

Assessment of Psychometric Properties of Teacher-made Mathematics Test for Continuous Assessment in Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State

Emmanuel, Ogidis Musa¹

ogidisbubba@gmail.com,
07034427225, 07011334915.

Lega, Asoloko Ezekiel¹

legaezekiel@gmail.com,
08139670065, 08083995220.

¹Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Federal University of lafia, Nasarawa state- Nigeria

Abstract

This article assessed the psychometric properties of teacher-made mathematics tests for continuous assessment in senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State. The study adopted descriptive survey research design, two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses were tested. The study employed simple random sampling to select 396 students (male:198 & female: 198) in SS II as respondents across the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State during the 2023/2024 academic session. Teachers-made Mathematics Test (TMT) consisted of 30 items constructed by secondary school teachers in various schools in Nasarawa State was used for data collection. The consensus validity rates of three experts on TMT yielded logical index of 0.76. The instrument was trial-tested using three Secondary Schools, from each of the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State. The split-halve method of calculating reliability was used to calculate the coefficient of internal consistency which gave 0.75. The result shows that the teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in mathematics for both male and female are moderately difficult, and there is no significant difference in the difficulty indices of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as segregated by gender in Nasarawa State. It was recommended that problematic items such as items with ambiguous wording and wrongly keyed should be reviewed to improve the quality of the tests for both male and female students and IRT analysis should be employed by teachers to improve on the poor item analysis of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as dichotomized by school locations in Nasarawa State.

Keywords: assessment, psychometric, properties, mathematics, teacher-made test.

Introduction

Education is one of the essential indices of development to any nation. The challenges faced as a result of fast changing and dynamic world necessitates the need to always access the educational process in to achieve quality of educational assessment. Assessment is the best basis for making inferences about the learning progress of students. It is used for measuring ability, achievement, interest and other traits. It could be a set of questions, tasks or problems constructed with the intention to measure the level of an individual's knowledge, skill, aptitude, intelligence, etc. Assessment should be considered as a measuring instrument (Anikweze, 2013). It covers all experiences both within and outside in the cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains of learning.

In section 1 of the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), which deals with the philosophy and goals of education in Nigeria, paragraph 9(g) states that “educational assessment and evaluation shall be liberalized by their being based in whole or in part on continuous assessment of the progress of the individual” (p.9). This statement is well amplified in subsequent sections of the document dealing with Primary Education (Section 4), Secondary Education (Section 5), Tertiary Education - (Section 5) and finally in Section 12 which deals with the Planning, Administration and Supervision of Education. Psychometric properties of tests are the quantifiable aspects of tests that indicate their statistical strengths and weaknesses. Psychometric properties are the intrinsic components of tests that reveal information about the relevance, adequacy and usefulness of tests.

Omole (2012) defined psychometric properties of a test as certain in characteristics inherent in the test upon which an assessment of a candidate is based. These properties include the facility, difficulty and discrimination indices, the power of distracters, validity and reliability indices. Some students hold notions that Mathematics as a science subject is an abstract subject to them. It is a body of knowledge that includes topics of numbers, shapes, formulas and spaces. It is among the

compulsory subjects offered in secondary schools and it is one of the core courses required by JAMB for the entry into tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Comprehensively, continuous assessment focuses on academic skills as well as cognitive and psychomotor domains. A child is assessed as a total entity using all psychometric devices like test and non-test techniques. Continuous assessment has cumulative characteristics because it gathers all the information on the individual together before a decision can be taken. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) defines continuous assessment as:

A mechanism whereby the final grading of a student in cognitive affective and psychomotor domains of behavior takes account in a systematic way, of all his performances during a given period of schooling such an assignment involves the use of great variety of modes of evaluation for the purpose of guiding and improving learning and performance of students (P.57).

Teacher-Made Test is an alternative to a standardized test, constructed and administered by the teacher in order to measure students' comprehension of the contents being taught. It enables students to demonstrate what they know and are capable of doing. Teacher-made tests are mostly used for the purpose of formative evaluation in secondary schools.

Obinne, (2011) studied on the psychometric analysis of two major examinations in Nigeria: standard error of measurement (SEM). The study centres on the psychometric analysis of two major examinations conducted in Nigeria by NECO and WAEC. The objective of the study was to compare the SEM of Biology examinations conducted from 2000–2002 using the one-parameter model of Item Response Theory (IRT). That SEM is commonly used to produce confidence interval and it is an estimate of how much error there is in a test. Instrumentation research design was used for the study. The population for the study comprised all year three (SSIII) senior secondary school students who enrolled for May/June/July 2006 Biology SSSCE of NECO and WAEC in the three education zones of Benue State. The sample for the study was one thousand eight hundred (1800) students. Multi-stage stratified sampling technique was used to arrive at the sample. NECO and WAEC 2000–2002 objective Biology questions were the instruments for the study. The maximum likelihood estimation techniques of the BILOG MG Computer Program and the SPSS were used for data analysis. The results showed significant differences in the SEM of Biology examinations conducted by NECO and WAEC in 2000, 2001 and 2002. This implied that Biology examinations conducted by NECO had smaller SEM (high reliability) than those of WAEC. It was recommended that IRT analysis should be employed by Nigerian examination bodies.

Kolawole & Ala; (2013) examined the predictive validity of continuous assessment score of students' performances in mathematics in some selected states in the South-West Nigeria. Continuous Assessment Scores (CA) were compared with the performance of students who sat for the Senior School Certificate Examination conducted by National Examinations Council (NECO) using June/July 2010 Senior School Certificate Examination (SSCE) as case study. Scores which were obtained from NECO had been transformed and trial-tested for psychometric properties. Six research questions were generated giving rise to six hypotheses which were tested at $\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance. The data used were analysed using descriptive statistics of means, standard deviation and inferential statistics of regression analysis. It was found that there was a positive but significant influence of Actual Aggregate Continuous Assessment (AACA) and Examination Scores on the Final Score. And also, there was a positive and significant influence of Moderated Aggregate Continuous Assessment Scores (MACA) and Examination Scores on Final Scores. They also found that AACA and Examinations Scores combined had the ability to predict the Final Grade as well as the combination of both MACA and Examination Scores. AACA and Examination score had positive and significant effect on. Final Scores as well as on MACA and Examination Scores. They however found that AACA and Examination Score had negative effect on Final Grade as well as MACA and Examination Scores combined.

Kiragu & Luke (2014), investigated the validity and reliability of teacher-made tests: through a case study of year 11 physics students in Nyahururu District of Kenya. The study was carried out to establish the factors influencing the validity and reliability of teacher made tests in Kenya. It was conducted in Nyahururu District of Laikipia County in Kenya. The study involved 42 teachers and 15 key informants selected from teachers holding various positions of academic responsibilities in their schools in Nyahururu District. A mixed descriptive survey research design was applied. Data was collected through questionnaires and interviews with key informants. Quantitative data analysis was applied to survey data collected via questionnaires. The frequency distribution was described while data from interviews were qualitatively analyzed. The findings of the study revealed that the experience of teachers, training on test construction and analysis, level of education, use of Bloom's taxonomy, moderation of tests and length of tests have an effect on validity and reliability of the tests. It was concluded that teacher-made tests are generally valid and reliable.

Oribhabor & Emafo (2016) Determining the Reliability and Content Validity of the Mathematics Tests Constructed by Senior Secondary School Mathematics Teachers in Edo State. The study assessed the quality of tests constructed by Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State. Samples of mathematics tests constructed by Senior

Secondary School Two (SS2) Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria were used. The purpose of the study was to ascertain whether the tests are sufficiently valid and reliable to make decisions about students' learning. The research design employed for the study was a survey design in which the Mathematics tests constructed by Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area were collected and analyzed. The population for this study included all the Senior Secondary Schools Two (SS2) Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State. The population of the study also includes all the Senior Secondary Schools Two (SS2) students in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State. The sample for the study has thirty-six (36) senior secondary two (SS2) Mathematics teachers who were randomly selected from the private senior secondary schools in Egor Local Government Area, Edo State. Thirty-six (36) Mathematics teachers were randomly selected from 102 private senior secondary schools in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. The instruments used for the collection of data for the study were copies of multiple-choice Mathematics achievement tests constructed by Mathematics teachers in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State and their students' marked answer scripts at the end of 2012/2013 academic session. Cronbach coefficient alpha was calculated for the results of all the tests which were accompanied with students' marked answer scripts. The content validity was established through expert agreement determined through Kendall Coefficient of concordance. Two Mathematics specialists and the researcher labeled - rater 1, rater 2 and rater 3, rated the content-related validity evidence of the tests using a 10-point scale. A rating of 1 indicates very low content validity and a rating of 10 indicates very high content-related validity. The results obtained indicate that the tests have moderate internal consistency reliability and low in content validity.

Mathematics is a discipline, which has been in existence for long time, and it arose from the needs of the people. The federal government of Nigeria has serious concern for the low standard of Mathematics education in the nation's schools, likewise the Nasarawa state government. Parents and teachers likewise are worried about the Mathematics results obtained by students in the school certificate examinations. The use of poorly designed teacher-made Mathematics test could be a major problem as it affects students' interest and achievement in Mathematics in their final examinations which may be WAEC, NECO and/or NABTEB examinations. For this reason, there is need to carry out a study with a view to determining the authenticity of teacher-made test for continuous assessment in Senior Secondary Schools. The thrust of this study is to assess the psychometric properties; difficulty, discrimination and distracter analysis of a teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment in Nasarawa State.

Objectives of the Study

The study intends to:

1. Compare difficulty indices of items in teacher-made mathematics tests for continuous assessment when segregated by gender.
2. Estimate the discrimination coefficient of each of the items in teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment in the urban and rural schools.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. How sensitive are the difficulty indices of the items in teacher-made mathematic tests used for continuous assessment when segregated by gender?
2. What are the discrimination coefficients of the items in the teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment with regard to urban and rural schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested for the study:

1. There is no significant difference in difficulty indices of items in teacher-made mathematics tests for continuous assessment when segregated by gender.
2. There is no significant difference in discrimination coefficient of each items in teacher-made mathematics tests used for continuous assessment in Urban and Rural schools.

Methodology

This study used descriptive survey research design to determine the nature of the psychometric properties of teacher-made tests for continuous assessment in mathematics for SS II in Nasarawa State. The population of this study comprised all the secondary school mathematics students in Nasarawa State. The study used simple random technique to select 396 respondents (male:198 & female: 198) across the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State. Teachers-made Mathematics Test

(TMT) consisted of 30 items constructed by teachers in various schools in Nasarawa State was used for data collection. The validity rate of the appraisal of three experts on TMT yielded logical index of **0.76**. The instrument was trial-tested using three Secondary Schools, from each of the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State. The split-half method of calculating reliability was used to calculate the coefficient of internal consistency which gave **0.75**.

Results

Research Question 1

Table 1: The Difficulty Indices of Teacher-made Mathematics Test used for Continuous Assessment for Male and Female Students in the senior secondary schools in Nasarawa State

Item	Male	Female	Item	Male	Female	Item	Male	Female
1.	0.56	0.63	11.	0.50	0.51	21.	0.35	0.45
2.	0.61	0.66	12.	0.50	0.49	22.	0.46	0.46
3.	0.61	0.65	13.	0.47	0.63	23.	0.39	0.43
4.	0.55	0.62	14.	0.47	0.55	24.	0.42	0.44
5.	0.59	0.65	15.	0.46	0.41	25.	0.42	0.39
6.	0.55	0.59	16.	0.47	0.49	26.	0.42	0.47
7.	0.49	0.53	17.	0.44	0.52	27.	0.42	0.44
8.	0.48	0.59	18.	0.40	0.40	28.	0.43	0.48
9.	0.60	0.58	19.	0.47	0.39	29.	0.45	0.39
10.	0.49	0.54	20.	0.37	0.46	30.	0.53	0.56
							0.479	0.513

Table 1 contains the means of the difficulty indices for the teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment for male and female students was calculated to be 0.48 and 0.51 respectively.

Research Question 2

Table 2: Item Discriminative Tests Data for 27% Upper Students Scores and 27% Lower Students Scores for Teacher-made Mathematics Tests used for Continuous Assessment in the Senior Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State

Item	Urban	Rural	Item	Urban	Rural	Item	Urban	Rural
1.	0.07	0.11	11.	0.11	0.06	21.	0.04	0.02
2.	0.08	0.07	12.	0.04	0.08	22.	0.03	0.08
3.	0.07	0.11	13.	0.11	0.02	23.	0.06	0.04
4.	0.10	0.07	14.	0.05	0.05	24.	0.03	0.10
5.	0.11	0.08	15.	0.08	0.02	25.	0.09	0.04
6.	0.10	0.06	16.	0.11	0.05	26.	0.10	0.04
7.	0.06	0.13	17.	0.09	0.05	27.	0.02	0.04
8.	0.09	0.09	18.	0.12	0.03	28.	0.12	0.01
9.	0.08	0.08	19.	0.03	0.08	29.	0.04	0.02
10.	0.08	0.11	20.	0.06	0.05	30.	0.08	0.06

Table 2 is 27% Upper Students and 27% Lower Students Discrimination indices for Teacher-made Mathematics Tests used for Continuous Assessment in the urban and rural areas of Nasarawa state.

Hypothesis 1

Table 3: Independent Samples t-test for Male Students Difficulty Indices and Female Students Difficulty Indices in Nasarawa State

Levene's test for equality of variances for male and female secondary school students' difficulty indices indicated equal variances since the sig value of 0.09 was greater than the 0.05. The male students' difficulty index compared to the female students' difficulty index has a t-value of -1.681 with 58 degree of freedom on a 2-tailed test with a mean difference of -0.03433

and a standard error different of 0.02042 with a 95% Confidence Interval of the difference of -0.07522 and 0.00655 for the lower and upper boundaries respectively.

Hypothesis 2

Table 4: Independent Samples t-test for Urban and Rural Students' Discrimination Coefficient of the Teacher-made Mathematics Tests used for Continuous Assessment in Secondary Schools in Nasarawa State

Levene's test for equality of variances with regard to urban and rural secondary school students' discrimination coefficient shew equal variances since the sig value of 0.780 was greater than the 0.05. The urban students' discrimination coefficient compared to the rural students' discrimination coefficient has a t-value of -1.327 with 58 degree of freedom on a 2-tailed test with a mean difference of 0.1133 and a standard error different of 0.00854 with a 95% Confidence Interval of the Difference of -0.00576 and 0.02842 for the lower and upper boundaries respectively as depicted in Table 4.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1, analysis of data shew that the teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in mathematics for both male and female are moderately difficult, since the 30 items for both the male and the female are in the level of moderate which is between 0.20 hand 0.90. Table 2, indicated that the discrimination indices of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in the senior secondary schools are poor in terms of discrimination indices and need to be improved upon since all the 30 items were poor items and needed to be rejected or improved. The study is in line with that of Oribhabor and Emafo (2016) that determined the reliability and content validity of the mathematics tests constructed by Senior Secondary School Mathematics Teachers in Edo State. The results obtained indicate that the tests have moderate internal consistency reliability and low in content validity. Ut it disagrees with that of Kiragu and Luke (2014) that investigated the validity and reliability of teacher-made tests: through a case study of year 11 physics students in Nyahururu District of Kenya, which concluded that teacher-made tests are generally valid and reliable.

Hypothesis 1 in table 3 revealed that the Sig (2-tailed) t-test value of 0.098 greater than 0.05 i.e. ($0.098 > 0.05$) with equal variances assumed [$t_{(58)} = -1.681, p = 0.098$]. The significant value of 0.098 was greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis 1 was not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the difficulty indices of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as segregated by gender in Nasarawa State. Hypothesis 2 in table 4 shew that the Sig. (2-tailed) t-test value of 0.780 greater than 0.05 i.e. ($0.780 > 0.05$) with equal variances assumed [$t_{(58)} = -1.327, p = 0.199$]. The significant value of 0.190 was greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis 2 was not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the discrimination coefficient of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as dichotomized by location in *Nasarawa State*.

Conclusion

In view of the findings from this study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in mathematics for both male and female are moderately difficult. Furthermore, the discrimination indices of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment in the senior secondary schools are poor in terms of discrimination indices and need to be improved.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings:

1. Problematic items such as items with ambiguous wording and wrongly keyed should be reviewed to improve the quality of the tests for both male and female students in Nasarawa State.
2. IRT analysis should be employed by rural as well as urban areas teachers to improve on the poor item analysis of teacher-made mathematics test used for continuous assessment as dichotomized by location in *Nasarawa State*.

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